

Statistical Identification of Risk and Protective Factors for Colorectal Neoplasia

Periklis Papias¹, Stergiani Viseri¹, Christos Androutsos¹, Traianos Tsiokris¹, Zheshen Jiang², Nicolas Gillain², Ioannis S. Papanikolaou³, Eleni Koukoulioti³, Constantina Cloconi⁴, Antria Savva⁴, Susanne F. Jørgensen⁵, Sisse H. Njor⁵, Maja Ravnik⁶, Sergej Černičič⁶, María González Oter^{7,8}, Raquel Alcaraz Ortega⁸, Dimitrios Kypreos⁹, Vasilis Giannakopoulos⁹, Dimitrios Dimitroulopoulos⁹, Stavros T. Miloulis¹⁰, Maria Haritou¹⁰, George K. Matsopoulos¹⁰, Dimitrios I. Fotiadis^{1,11}

¹ Unit of Medical Technology and Intelligent Information Systems, Dept. of Materials Science and Engineering, University of Ioannina, Ioannina, Greece

² Department of Information System Management, Hospital Center of University of Liège, Liège, Belgium

³ Hepatogastroenterology Unit, Second Department of Internal Medicine, National and Kapodistrian University, Attikon University General Hospital, Athens, Greece

⁴ Radiation Oncology Center, German Oncology Center

⁵ Lillebaelt Hospital, Research Unit for Screening and Epidemiology, Department of Biochemistry and Immunology, Denmark University of Southern Denmark, Department of Regional Health Research, Denmark.

⁶ Department of Oncology, University Medical Centre Maribor, Maribor, Slovenia

⁷ Cancer Genetics Group, Unit of Excellence Institute of Biomedicine and Molecular Genetics,

University of Valladolid Spanish National Research Council (IBGM; UVA-CSIC), 47003 Valladolid, Spain

⁸ Unidad de Investigación, Hospital Universitario de Burgos, Burgos, España

⁹ Agios Savvas, Cancer Hospital, Athens, Greece

¹⁰ Biomedical Engineering Laboratory, School of Electrical and Computer Engineering, National Technological University of Athens, Athens, Greece

¹¹ Biomedical Research Institute, FORTH, Ioannina, Greece

Abstract—Colorectal cancer is a major public health burden in Europe, with a risk influenced by demographic, lifestyle, clinical and medication-related factors. Most existing studies assess colorectal cancer risk using binary comparisons, potentially overlooking important variations across intermediate groups of colorectal neoplasia. This study presents a statistical framework for identifying risk and protective factors across the colorectal neoplasia spectrum. Data from a retrospective clinical study and a prospective biomarker discovery study were integrated, comprising four groups. Associations between multiple features and increasing group severity were assessed using univariate analysis and multivariable ordinal regression. The proportional odds assumption was formally evaluated, and a partial proportional odds model was applied to accommodate predictors exhibiting non-parallel effects across severity thresholds. Findings reveal that increasing age, male sex, smoking status, alcohol consumption, cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus and dyslipidemia were associated with higher odds of more severe groups. In contrast, the use of aspirin, statins and anticoagulants was associated with lower odds of colorectal neoplasia. Accounting for heterogeneity in risk factor effects across groups,

the proposed approach provides a statistically robust assessment of colorectal cancer risk. These findings support improved risk stratification strategies and motivate further prospective investigation in broader screening populations.

Index Terms—Colorectal cancer, risk factors, protective factors, multivariate analysis, ordinal logistic regression, partial proportional odds model

I. INTRODUCTION

Colorectal Cancer (CRC) ranks as the third most commonly diagnosed cancer globally and the second leading cause of cancer-related mortality [1]. CRC development is influenced by both non-modifiable and modifiable risk factors. Non-modifiable factors include age, sex, ethnicity, inflammatory bowel disease and family history of CRC. In contrast, modifiable risk factors are primarily related to lifestyle behaviors, such as tobacco use, alcohol consumption and unhealthy dietary patterns [1], [2].

Tsukanov et al. [3] summarized evidence indicating that obesity, sedentary lifestyle and unhealthy dietary patterns are consistently identified as modifiable risk factors for CRC. These associations are thought to be mediated through chronic systemic inflammation, insulin resistance, metabolic dysregulation and altered gastrointestinal physiology. Furthermore, Zhang et al. [6], in a study including 17,662 individuals and using logistic regression analysis, reported that smoking

Funded by the European Union (DIOPTRA, 101096649). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the Health and Digital Executive Agency. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them. This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI). Funded by UK Research and Innovation (UKRI) under the UK government's Horizon Europe funding guarantee [grant number 10056682].

and chronic lung disease were significantly associated with increased odds of CRC.

In contrast, several pharmacological exposures have been proposed as potential protective factors. Protective factors are typically defined as exposures associated with a reduced risk of CRC development or progression [18], [19]. Sleiman et al. [4], in a cohort study including 11,354 patients and using logistic regression analysis, reported that statin use was associated with lower odds of CRC. Moreover, when compared with aspirin-only users, the combined use of statins and aspirin was associated with significantly lower odds of colorectal cancer, suggesting a potential synergistic protective association.

Although numerous epidemiological studies have examined CRC risk factors most analyses rely on binary comparisons between healthy individuals and CRC patients [6], potentially overlooking important variations in risk factor profiles across intermediate groups of colorectal neoplasia.

This work presents a statistical framework that integrates univariate and multivariate analyses to investigate risk and protective factors across the colorectal neoplasia spectrum utilising a homogenised multicenter CRC dataset. By modeling four diagnostic groups such as healthy individuals, Non-Advanced Adenomas (N-AA), Advanced Adenomas (AA), and CRC patients, the proposed approach captures the progressive nature of colorectal neoplasia beyond traditional binary comparisons. In particular, the application of a Partial Proportional Odds model enables the identification of both stable and severity-dependent associations while appropriately accounting for violations of the proportional odds assumption. Through this methodology, the study aims to enhance risk stratification strategies and provide insights that may inform future preventive and clinical decision-making efforts.

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

A. Dataset Description

The presented work integrates data from two complementary study components of the DIOPTRA project: a retrospective, multicenter clinical study and a prospective biomarker discovery study. Both studies received approval from the appropriate institutional ethics committees at all participating clinical centers. The retrospective study provided the core clinical, demographic, medication-related, and colonoscopic data for individuals who underwent colonoscopy across multiple clinical sites. Lifestyle-related data as well as selected medical history information were obtained from participants of the biomarker discovery study, who completed two structured questionnaires. Questionnaire responses were subsequently harmonized and integrated with the retrospective clinical dataset.

Standard data preprocessing and cleaning procedures were applied. After preprocessing, the final dataset contained no missing values across the selected features, ensuring consistency and stability in the subsequent statistical analysis. A total of 5,093 individuals were included in the analysis, comprising 1,539 healthy participants, 1,454 with N-AA, 848 with AA, and 1,251 CRC patients. The study population included 1,839

women and 3,254 men. The mean age of women was 60.34 years (SD = 11.64), while the mean age of men was 61.79 years (SD = 10.53).

For each participant, a total of 24 features were recorded, including 23 input features encompassing demographic, clinical, lifestyle-related, and medication-related domains, along with one outcome variable corresponding to the diagnosis. The outcome was categorized into four ordered groups reflecting increasing disease severity such as Healthy individuals, N-AA, AA and CRC patients. This ordinal classification reflects the natural progression of colorectal neoplasia from benign lesions to malignant transformation and provides a clinically meaningful framework for statistical modeling. The input features were grouped into the following categories:

- **Demographic features** included age at the time of colonoscopy and sex.
- **Clinical features** included cardiovascular disease, diabetes mellitus type 2, hypertension, dyslipidemia, chronic kidney disease and allergy/asthma status.
- **Medication-related features** included the use of aspirin, statins, anticoagulants, antihypertensive medications, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs (NSAIDs), antiplatelet agents, insulin, glucagon-like peptide-1 receptor agonists (GLP-1), sodium–glucose cotransporter-2 inhibitors (SGLT-2), metformin, dipeptidyl peptidase-4 inhibitors (DPP-4), corticosteroids, and allergy-related medications.
- **Lifestyle-related features** included smoking status and drinking behavior.

Among the selected features, age at the time of colonoscopy was the only continuous numerical variable. Two features were categorical nominal variables: smoking status, categorized as 0 = never smoker, 1 = current smoker, and 2 = former smoker; and allergy/asthma status, categorized as 0 = no allergy or asthma, 1 = allergy only, 2 = asthma only, and 3 = both allergy and asthma. All remaining features were binary variables, indicating the presence or absence of the corresponding condition or medication use.

B. Statistical Analysis

Statistical analysis was conducted in two complementary stages. First, univariate and bivariate analyses were performed to explore the structure of the dataset, assess crude associations between individual features and colorectal neoplasia and gain an initial understanding of potential risk and protective factors. These exploratory analyses were used to support interpretation and guide subsequent modeling, but were not intended for definitive inference. Second, multivariate regression analysis was applied to simultaneously account for multiple covariates and to derive adjusted associations with the four groups. All final conclusions regarding risk and protective factors were based exclusively on the results of the multivariate analysis.

1) *Univariate / Bivariate Analysis*: Univariate and bivariate analyses were conducted to explore the structure of the dataset and to obtain an initial understanding of potential

risk and protective factors associated with colorectal neoplasia. This exploratory analysis aimed to identify crude associations between individual features and the diagnosis, to assess distributional properties of the variables, and to provide contextual interpretation for the results of the subsequent multivariate analysis. Importantly, findings from this stage were not intended for causal inference, but rather to inform and support the interpretation of adjusted effects derived from the multivariate model.

For categorical (qualitative) variables, associations with the diagnosis outcome were assessed using the chi-squared test [14] of independence based on contingency tables. When statistically significant associations were identified, Adjusted Standardized Residuals (ASR) [14] were examined to determine which specific category of the diagnosis combinations contributed to the observed dependence. Values of $|\text{ASR}| > 1.96$ were considered indicative of statistically significant deviations from independence and were used to highlight potential risk-enhancing or protective patterns across groups.

For quantitative variables, the analysis focused exclusively on age, which was the only numerical feature in the dataset. Age was compared across the four groups following an initial assessment for outliers within each group. Given that the sample size of each diagnostic category far exceeded 50 observations, statistical inference was conducted under the Central Limit Theorem [7], allowing parametric methods to be applied. Homogeneity of variances across the groups was evaluated using Levene’s test [8]. When the assumption of equal variances was satisfied, a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) [9] was employed, otherwise, Welch’s ANOVA [9] was used. In cases where statistically significant differences were detected, post hoc analyses [10] were performed to identify specific differences in age across the groups.

2) *Multivariate Analysis*: Multivariate analysis was conducted to identify risk and protective factors associated with increasing colorectal neoplasia, while appropriately accounting for the ordinal nature of the diagnosis. Prior to model fitting, categorical nominal variables were suitably encoded to allow their inclusion in regression-based models. Specifically, smoking status and the allergies/asthma variable were transformed using one-hot encoding. To avoid the dummy variable trap and ensure model identifiability, the first category of each nominal variable was used as the reference level and was therefore omitted from the design matrix.

Given that diagnosis consists of four ordered groups, ordinal regression models were considered. Initially, the proportional odds assumption was evaluated to determine whether a standard Ordinal Logistic Regression (OLR) model [15] was appropriate. This assumption implies that the effect of each predictor is constant across all cumulative splits of the ordinal outcome. In other words, the regression coefficients are assumed to be identical for each binary comparison of the ordered groups. To formally assess this assumption, the Brant test [11] was applied. The Brant test evaluates, for each predictor, whether the proportional odds assumption holds across all cut-points of the outcome.

Fig. 1. Overview of the statistical analysis workflow for identifying risk and protective factors across colorectal neoplasia.

Predictors with a Brant test p-value lower than 0.05 were classified as non-parallel, indicating that their effects vary across group thresholds. Conversely, predictors with p-values greater than or equal to 0.05 were classified as parallel, reflecting stable effects across groups. In the present dataset, the Brant test revealed the presence of multiple non-parallel predictors. As a result, the proportional odds assumption was violated, rendering the standard OLR model inappropriate. To accommodate this violation while preserving the ordinal structure of the outcome, a Partial Proportional Odds Model (PPOM) [11] was employed. The PPOM allows predictors that satisfy the proportional odds assumption to retain a common effect across thresholds, while permitting non-parallel predictors to have threshold-specific effects.

The PPOM is based on a cumulative logit formulation, in which the log-odds of being at or above a given diagnostic threshold are modeled as a function of both parallel and non-parallel predictors. Specifically, for each cumulative threshold j , the model is defined as

$$\log \left(\frac{\Pr(Y \geq j)}{\Pr(Y < j)} \right) = \alpha_j + \beta X_{\text{parallel}} + \gamma_j X_{\text{nonparallel}},$$

with $j \in \{2, 3, 4\}$ [16]. Here, Y denotes the diagnosis with increasing values corresponding to more severe groups and α_j represents a threshold-specific intercept. Also, β denotes the vector of regression coefficients associated with the parallel

predictors X_{parallel} , which are assumed to have a common effect across all cumulative thresholds, consistent with the proportional odds assumption. In contrast, γ_j represents the threshold-specific regression coefficients corresponding to the non-parallel predictors $X_{\text{nonparallel}}$, allowing their effects to vary across the cumulative logits.

Consequently, while the impact of the parallel predictors on the odds of being at or above a given diagnostic category remains constant across thresholds, the influence of the non-parallel predictors may differ depending on the severity level j . The model yields three cumulative comparisons corresponding to the transitions from healthy to (N-AA, AA, CRC), from (healthy, N-AA) to (AA, CRC) and from (healthy, N-AA, AA) to CRC.

For predictors that violate the proportional odds assumption (non-parallel variables), the model estimates separate odds ratios for each diagnostic threshold, allowing their effects to vary across groups. In contrast, predictors that satisfy the proportional odds assumption (parallel variables) are constrained to have a single common odds ratio that applies uniformly across all thresholds. This structure enables flexible modeling of heterogeneous risk patterns while preserving the ordinal nature of colorectal disease progression.

Additionally, because regression-based models may be sensitive to multicollinearity among predictors, the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) [12] was computed for all input features. This method was utilised to assess the presence of linear dependencies between covariates and to ensure the numerical stability and interpretability of the estimated regression coefficients. No evidence of problematic multicollinearity was detected. All multivariate statistical analyses were conducted at a significance level of $\alpha = 0.05$ and results were reported using 95% CIs.

III. RESULTS

The multivariate analysis was conducted using a PPOM to account for violations of the proportional odds assumption identified during model diagnostics. The Brant test indicated that several features exhibited non-parallel effects, meaning that their associations with the outcome varied across group thresholds. These non-parallel features included age at colonoscopy, cardiovascular disease, sex, smoking status (previous smoking), drinking behavior, dyslipidemia, use of allergy-related medications, and use of antihypertensive medications. All remaining features satisfied the proportional odds assumption and were therefore modeled as having constant effects across disease severity levels.

The PPOM was fitted using a logit link function [20] corresponding to the logistic cumulative distribution function and yielding regression coefficients interpretable on the log-odds scale. Model parameters were estimated via maximum likelihood using the Broyden–Fletcher–Goldfarb–Shanno (BFGS) optimization algorithm [12], a gradient-based numerical method. Results are reported as odds ratios (ORs) with corresponding 95% CIs, with statistical significance assessed at a 5% significance level.

A. Risk Factors

1) Non-Parallel Risk Factors:

Age at Colonoscopy

Increasing age was associated with significantly higher odds of belonging to more severe groups across all thresholds, with effect sizes decreasing as group severity increased. Specifically, for the transition from healthy to N-AA, each one-year increase in age was associated with a 6.3% increase in odds (OR = 1.063, 95% CI : 1.055–1.070, $p < 0.001$). For the transition to AA, the corresponding increase was 4.3% per year (OR = 1.043, 95% CI : 1.037–1.051, $p < 0.001$), while for the transition to CRC the increase was 3.1% per year (OR = 1.031, 95% CI : 1.023–1.039, $p < 0.001$).

Previous Smoking

Compared with never smokers, former smokers had significantly higher odds of more severe groups of colorectal neoplasia. Specifically, former smoking was associated with increased odds of belonging to any group (N-AA or AA or CRC) compared with healthy individuals (OR = 2.33, 95% CI : 1.72–3.15, $p < 0.001$). For the transition to AA, the association became stronger with almost three and a half fold increase in odds compared with any of the other two groups (healthy or N-AA) (OR = 3.54, 95% CI : 2.77–4.52, $p < 0.001$). The strongest effect was observed for CRC patients, where previous smoking was associated with an almost fourfold increase in odds compared with the rest groups (OR = 3.81, 95% CI : 3.01–4.83, $p < 0.001$).

Drinking Behavior

Current drinkers, compared with non-drinkers, had significantly higher odds of more severe groups of colorectal neoplasia. Specifically, current drinking was associated with increased odds of belonging to any group (N-AA, AA, CRC) compared with healthy individuals (OR = 1.51, 95% CI : 1.07–2.12, $p = 0.018$). For the transition to AA, the association strengthened, with approximately a twofold increase in odds (OR = 2.10, 95% CI : 1.60–2.76, $p < 0.001$). The strongest effect was observed for CRC patients, where current drinking was associated with more than a two and a half fold increase in odds compared with the rest groups (OR = 2.65, 95% CI : 2.04–3.45, $p < 0.001$).

Sex

Males compared to females, was associated with increased odds of less severe groups, with diminishing effects at more severe groups. Specifically, males had more than twofold higher odds of belonging to any group (N-AA, AA, CRC) compared with healthy individuals (OR = 2.13, 95% CI : 1.87–2.44, $p < 0.001$). For the transition to AA, the association remained statistically significant but was attenuated, corresponding to a 29% increase in odds compared with any of the two groups (healthy or N-AA) (OR = 1.29, 95% CI : 1.13–1.47, $p = 0.001$). In contrast, no statistically significant association between sex and CRC patients was observed (OR = 0.96, 95% CI : 0.82–1.12, $p = 0.603$).

Cardiovascular Disease

Cardiovascular disease exhibited a non-parallel association with group severity, with effect sizes increasing markedly across group thresholds. Specifically, individuals with cardiovascular disease had nearly double the odds of belonging to any group (N-AA, AA, CRC) compared with healthy individuals (OR = 1.91, 95% CI : 1.54–2.36, $p < 0.001$). For the transition to advanced adenoma, the association strengthened further, with more than a twofold increase in odds compared with any of the two groups (healthy or N-AA) (OR = 2.21, 95% CI : 1.85–2.63, $p < 0.001$). The strongest effect was observed for CRC patients, where cardiovascular disease was associated with an almost fourfold increase in odds compared with the rest groups (OR = 3.74, 95% CI : 3.11–4.50, $p < 0.001$).

Dyslipidemia

Dyslipidemia exhibited a non-parallel association with group severity, with its effect becoming evident at more severe groups. No statistically significant association was observed between dyslipidemia and the transition from healthy to N-AA (OR = 1.05, 95% CI : 0.88–1.25, $p = 0.590$). In contrast, dyslipidemia was significantly associated with increased odds of severe groups. Specifically, individuals with dyslipidemia had a 45% increase in odds of belonging to any group (AA or CRC) compared with individuals who were either healthy or had N-AA (OR = 1.45, 95% CI : 1.19–1.79, $p < 0.001$). A similar association was observed for CRC patients with dyslipidemia associated with a 52% increase in odds compared with the rest groups (OR = 1.52, 95% CI : 1.22–1.90, $p < 0.001$).

2) *Parallel Risk Factors*: Two predictors exhibited parallel risk associations with colorectal neoplasia, indicating stable effects across all group thresholds. More precisely, Diabetes mellitus type 2 was associated with a 53% increase in the odds of belonging to more severe group (OR = 1.53, 95% CI : 1.19–1.96, $p < 0.001$). Former smoking status demonstrated a particularly strong association, with nearly a threefold increase in the odds across all groups (OR = 2.77, 95% CI : 2.13–3.59, $p < 0.001$). Both variables satisfied the proportional odds assumption, indicating that their effects remained constant across all group thresholds. The following table summarizes the parallel risk factors identified by the PPOM.

TABLE I
PARALLEL RISK FACTORS

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value
Diabetes mellitus type 2	1.53	1.19 - 1.96	< 0.001
Former smoking	2.77	2.13 - 3.59	< 0.001

B. Protective Factors

Some medications exhibited protective associations with group severity. The use of aspirin, statins and anticoagulants was associated with statistically significant lower odds of more severe groups, with stable effects across all thresholds. More precisely, aspirin use was associated with a 43% reduction

in the odds of more severe disease across all thresholds (OR = 0.57, 95% CI : 0.38–0.85, $p = 0.007$). Statin use was likewise associated with reduced odds of disease severity, corresponding to a 24% decrease in odds (OR = 0.76, 95% CI : 0.61–0.94, $p = 0.01$).

The strongest inverse association was observed for anti-coagulant use, which was associated with a 48% reduction in the odds of more severe diagnostic categories (OR = 0.52, 95% CI : 0.40–0.69, $p < 0.001$). All three medications satisfied the proportional odds assumption, indicating stable protective effects across all diagnostic thresholds. The following table summarizes these inverse associations.

TABLE II
PARALLEL PROTECTIVE FACTORS

Variable	OR	95% CI	p-value
Aspirin	0.57	0.38 - 0.85	0.007
Statin	0.76	0.61 - 0.94	0.01
Anticoagulants	0.52	0.40 - 0.69	< 0.001

IV. DISCUSSION

CRC remains one of the leading causes of cancer-related mortality worldwide, so improving our understanding of its risk determinants across the disease continuum is essential for advancing prevention and early detection strategies. Although several risk and protective factors for CRC have been previously described, evidence derived from large, clinically representative European populations remains limited. An additional strength of the present work is that it integrates data from four independent clinical centers across Europe, providing a diverse and multicenter perspective that enhances the generalizability of our findings.

Unlike the majority of existing studies, which identify colorectal cancer risk factors by comparing healthy individuals with CRC patients [17], or by using a limited number of disease categories [5], the present analysis examined four clinically meaningful groups to capture the progressive nature of colorectal neoplasia. This approach allowed the investigation of how risk factors evolve across the group severity rather than limiting inference to cancer endpoints.

Another important contribution of this study lies in the statistical framework employed. Initial univariate analysis were conducted to explore crude associations and guide interpretation. However, all inferential conclusions were derived from multivariate modeling. Crucially, instead of relying on the conventional OLR framework, the proportional odds assumption was tested using the Brant test and demonstrated that several predictors violated proportionality. To address this, the PPOM was implemented, which allowed selected predictors to vary across group thresholds while retaining proportionality for others. To our knowledge, this modeling strategy has seldom been applied in CRC risk analysis, particularly within a European multicenter cohort. Therefore it represents a methodological advancement that yields statistically valid and clinically insights.

The results of this study highlight distinct patterns of association between demographic, lifestyle, clinical, and medication-related factors and increasing severity across the colorectal neoplasia spectrum. Increasing age emerged as a strong determinant across all group transitions, with diminishing effect sizes at higher severity thresholds, reflecting the cumulative nature of CRC risk. Lifestyle-related factors, particularly smoking status and alcohol consumption, were consistently associated with higher odds of more severe groups, reinforcing their established role in colorectal neoplasia. Clinical comorbidities such as cardiovascular disease, type 2 diabetes mellitus, and dyslipidemia also demonstrated significant associations, with several exhibiting severity-dependent effects, suggesting that underlying metabolic and vascular conditions may contribute differentially across groups of neoplastic progression. In contrast, the use of aspirin, statins, and anticoagulants was associated with lower odds of advanced disease, with stable effects across thresholds, supporting existing evidence for their potential risk-reducing role. Importantly, the ordinal modeling framework enabled these associations to be examined across intermediate groups, providing a better understanding of how risk and risk-reducing factors operate along the colorectal neoplasia continuum.

This study should be interpreted in light of several limitations. First, although the multicenter design enhances representativeness, the analysis is restricted to individuals undergoing colonoscopy in clinical settings, who may differ from average-risk screening populations. Second, lifestyle-related variables were available only through the biomarker discovery study, and despite careful harmonization, differences in data collection modalities may introduce residual measurement variability. Third, the analysis relied on a predefined set of demographic, clinical, lifestyle, and medication-related variables, and did not include other potentially relevant factors such as detailed dietary information, physical activity, genetic susceptibility, or family history of colorectal cancer. As a result, the identified associations should be interpreted within the context of the available feature set. Finally, while the partial proportional odds model provides a flexible and statistically appropriate framework for ordinal outcomes, residual confounding from unmeasured variables cannot be fully excluded. Despite these limitations, the analytical approach enables a robust assessment of risk patterns across the colorectal neoplasia spectrum.

V. CONCLUSION

Overall, this work demonstrates that combining multicenter clinical data with ordinal statistical modeling enables refined risk stratification across the colorectal neoplasia continuum. Several clinical and lifestyle factors were associated with increased disease severity, whereas selected medications were linked to reduced odds of progression. The proposed methodological approach may support more refined prevention strategies and inform future prospective studies aimed at validating and extending these findings in broader screening populations.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The authors thank Prof. Apostolos Batsidis for his valuable discussions and contributions to this work.

REFERENCES

- [1] Y. He et al., "Global, regional and national burden of colon and rectum cancer: a systematic analysis of prevalence, incidence, deaths and DALYs from 1990 to 2021 using data from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2021 with projections to 2036," *BMJ Open*, vol. 15, no. 10, p. e100042, October 2025.
- [2] J. Zhou et al., "Evolving landscape of colorectal cancer: Global and regional burden, risk factor dynamics, and future scenarios (the Global Burden of Disease 1990-2050)," *Ageing Res. Rev.*, vol. 104, p. 102666, January 2025.
- [3] V. V. Tsukanov, A. V. Vasyutin, and J. L. Tonkikh, "Risk factors, prevention and screening of colorectal cancer: A rising problem," *World Journal of Gastroenterology*, vol. 31, no. 5, pp. 98629, February 2025.
- [4] J. Sleiman et al., "Chemopreventive Effects of Statins and Aspirin on Colorectal Cancer Among Patients with Inflammatory Bowel Disease: Evidence of a Synergistic Association from a Large Cohort," *Clin. Exp. Gastroenterol.*, vol. 18, pp. 277–290, November 2025.
- [5] J. Demb et al., "Risk factors for colorectal cancer significantly vary by anatomic site," *BMJ Open Gastroenterol.*, vol. 6, no. 1, p. e000313, August 2019.
- [6] L. Zhang et al., "Risk factors of colorectal cancer in middle-aged and elder adults in China: findings from the China health and retirement longitudinal study," *Front. Mol. Biosci.*, vol. 12, p. 1333834, April 2025.
- [7] W. W. Daniel and C. L. Cross, *Biostatistics: A foundation for analysis in the health sciences*, 10th ed., Hoboken, New Jersey, 2013, pp. 139-144
- [8] J. L. Gastwirth, Y. R. Gel, W. Miao, "The Impact of Levene's Test of Equality of Variances on Statistical Theory and Practice," *Statist. Sci.*, vol. 24, pp. 343 - 360, August 2009.
- [9] M. Delacre, C. Leys, Y. L. Mora and D.Lakens, "Taking Parametric Assumptions Seriously: Arguments for the Use of Welch's F-test instead of the Classical F-test in One-Way ANOVA," *International Review of Social Psychology*, vol. 32, 2019.
- [10] D. G. Pereira, A. Afonso and F. M. Medeiros, "Overview of Friedman's Test and Post-hoc Analysis," *Communications in Statistics - Simulation and Computation*, vol. 44, pp. 2636-2653, 2015.
- [11] B.T. Zewude and L. K. Debusho, "Multilevel proportional odds modeling of anaemia prevalence among under five years old children in Ethiopia," *BMC Public Health*, vol. 23, March 2023.
- [12] R. M. O'brien, "A Caution Regarding Rules of Thumb for Variance Inflation Factors," *Quality and Quantity*, vol. 41, pp. 673-690, March 2007.
- [13] N. M. Nawi, M. R. Ransing and R. S. Ransing, "An Improved Learning Algorithm Based on The Broyden-Fletcher-Goldfarb-Shanno (BFGS) Method For Back Propagation Neural Networks," *Sixth International Conference on Intelligent Systems Design and Applications*, Jian, China, 2006, pp. 152-157.
- [14] F.Z. Okwonu, N. A. Ahad, J. S. Apanapudor and F. I. Arunaye, "Chi-square and Adjusted Standardised Residual Analysis," *ASM Science Journal*, vol.18, 2023.
- [15] F. E. Harrell Jr., "Ordinal logistic regression," in *Regression modeling strategies*, 2nd ed., F. E. Harrell Jr., Ed. Cham: Springer, 2015, pp. 311–325.
- [16] R. Williams, "Generalized ordered logit/partial proportional odds models for ordinal dependent variables," *Stata J.*, vol. 6, no. 1, pp. 58–82, March 2006.
- [17] A. Lewandowska, G. Rudzki, T. Lewandowski, A. Strykowska-Gora, and S. Rudzki, "Risk factors for the diagnosis of colorectal cancer," *Cancer control*, vol. 29, 2022.
- [18] G. Roshandel, F. Ghasemi-Kebria and R. Malekzadeh, "Colorectal cancer: epidemiology, risk factors, and prevention. *Cancers*," vol. 16, April 2024.
- [19] Z. Ungvari, M. Fekete, J. T. Fekete, G. Grosso, A. Ungvari and B. Györfy, "Adherence to the Mediterranean diet and its protective effects against colorectal cancer: a meta-analysis of 26 studies with 2,217,404 participants," *Geroscience*, vol. 47, pp. 1105-1121, 2025.
- [20] F. Fernández-Navarro, (2017), "A generalized logistic link function for cumulative link models in ordinal regression," *Neural Processing Letters*, vol. 46, pp. 251-269, January 2017.